

A CORRELATIONAL STUDY ON THE EFFECTS OF INSTAGRAM INFLUENCER MARKETING ON PURCHASING INTENTIONS OF GRADE 12 ABM STUDENTS IN MANILA

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ABSTRACT

Many consumers rely on Instagram and other social media platforms for shopping, driven by influencers. However, research gaps exist in understanding physical attractiveness, product opinions, and follower counts. As a result, this study examined how Instagram influencers affect the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in Manila. The study selected respondents familiar with consumer behavior, aligning closely with the study's topic, and employed a correlational quantitative design. The study surveyed 138 students through simple random sampling and descriptive and correlational analysis. The results highlight the influence of physical attractiveness on consumers' perceptions of products endorsed by Instagram influencers. The results also demonstrate a strong positive effect of influencer marketing on purchase intentions among Grade 12 ABM students, confirming aspects of the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) related to follower count, product opinions, and visual appeal. Overall, the study affirmed that Instagram influencers significantly impact the purchasing intention of Grade 12 ABM students in Manila. Future researchers should use qualitative methods to explore students' purchasing intentions influenced by Instagram marketing, expanding their study to include various cities in Luzon and conducting comparative analyses across social media platforms to explore cultural influences.

Keywords: *Social media marketing, Social media, Instagram, Influencers, Purchasing Intention*

INTRODUCTION

The use of social media has been extensively studied in recent years; in some, it is used for marketing purposes to promote brand-related content (Jami Pour et al., 2021). Ever since the pandemic struck, social media use has been a necessity in our everyday lives. A study from Dollarhide (2023) states that people use social media for browsing the news, passing their time, and connecting with friends, and many marketers have taken advantage of this trend to market their products and create a new strategy in the marketing industry called social media marketing. Instagram has grown from a mere socializing social media platform to a useful tool for marketing intentions throughout the years (Pick, 2021). Due to the application's popularity, many brands took this as an opportunity to utilize the mobile application to increase their social media presence and engagement (Belanche et al., 2020). With the rising number of social media users' day by day, some users use this as their platform to give their feedback on certain products, they are called "social media influencers" (Hani et al., 2022). Through this, they can generate profit by being paid by the brands that wish for them to give their review on their items. As people continue to follow the lives of these influencers through their content, their purchasing intentions might be influenced as the influencers promote their products.

The surge in influencer marketing has prompted numerous research endeavors into the matter. However, a thorough scientific grasp of the subject still needs to be improved. Several reasons contribute to this gap in understanding. First, various researchers studied the purchasing intentions of social media users. However, these studies focus on a big age group in studying the purchasing intentions of social media users, disabling them to be specific in their research (Hani et al., 2018; Kim & Kim, 2023; Jami Pour et al., 2021). Second, prior researchers have yet to concentrate primarily on the purchasing intentions of social media users. Their focus has been split between purchasing intentions and various other variables, such as mental well-being (Staniewski & Awruk, 2022), brand loyalty (Balakrishnan et al., 2014), and brand attitude (Abzari et al., 2014), preventing them from entirely concentrating on the purchasing intentions of social media users. Third, the researchers noticed that limited studies concerning social media influencers contain the following variables: physical attractiveness, opinions on a product, and number of followers. Fourth, previous studies have also failed to determine whether Instagram influencers positively or negatively impact consumers' purchasing intentions (Masuda et al., 2022; Farivar & Wang, 2022; Sun et al., 2021). Lastly, a similar study pointed out that social media influencers contributed to consumers' impulsive buying behavior, negatively impacting consumers as they cannot decide comprehensively regarding the products they are about to purchase (Zafar et al., 2023).

In order to address the problems highlighted in the previous studies, a comprehensive study that is patterned to existing literature and in accordance with this study's objective is needed to address the specific gaps and problems that were identified by this paper.

With that, the study aimed to determine the effect of Instagram influencers as a form of social media marketing on the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila.

Research Questions

In relation to the theory being utilized in this study, the general objective of this study is to determine the effect of Instagram influencers as a form of social media marketing on the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. In order to address the general objective and specific objectives of this study that are patterned within the theoretical framework, specifically the theory of persuasion or Elaboration Likelihood Model Theory, the paper sought to satisfy the formulated main question:

How do Instagram influencers as a form of social media marketing affect the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 students of the ABM strand in a private university in Manila?

Furthermore, the study was inclined to address the following Sub-questions:

1. Which variable concerning Instagram Influencers affects the purchasing intention of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila, focusing on physical attractiveness, opinions on a product, and number of followers?
2. How do the physical attractiveness, opinions on a product, and number of followers of Instagram influencers affect the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila?
3. Is there a difference in the effect of Instagram influencers on the purchasing intention of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila based on gender?
4. Is there a relationship between the physical attractiveness of Instagram influencers and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila?
5. Is there a relationship between the opinions on a product of Instagram influencers and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila?
6. Is there a relationship between the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila and the number of followers of an Instagram influencer?

METHODOLOGY

The study used a quantitative approach to gather data from respondents through survey forms. Such a method aided researchers in determining the effects of Instagram influencers as a social media marketing tool on the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. Furthermore, the quantitative design enabled the researchers to unveil the relationships among variables, as Sreekumar (2023) pointed out. Specifically, the study adopted a correlational research design to gain a thorough and comprehensive understanding of the population or phenomenon under study, including identifying patterns and relationships that may exist among the variables

(Bhandari, 2022). The selection of this research design was attributed to its distinct advantages over other designs.

As the study determined the effects of Instagram influencers as a form of social media marketing on the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila, an accurate evaluation was required to explain better and understand the research objectives and problems. As a result, following the research design, ABM students from batch 2024 in a private university in Manila were chosen as the population of the respondents. This population comprised 213 students who were 18 years old or above 18. Considering the significant number of students, the researchers employed a probability sampling method to select the questionnaire respondents. Specifically, the researchers chose a simple random sampling method for this study. This approach entailed the selection of a random subset of a population, where each member has an equal chance of being chosen (Hayes, 2023).

The primary data collection for this study was through an online survey questionnaire that was disseminated through the use of Google forms. The survey comprised a comprehensive set of 24 self-developed questions, which underwent validation by an expert within the researchers' institution specifically from the ABM strand of a private university in Manila. Moreover, to ensure the survey's effectiveness in providing accurate and reliable data in examining the variables of this study, the researchers conducted a pilot test on a selected subset of respondents from the population.

The selected method for handling the ordinal data collected from an online questionnaire involved descriptive and correlational analysis. As Rawat (2021) elucidates, descriptive analysis aids in understanding data distribution, detecting potential errors and outliers, and uncovering relationships among variables, laying a strong groundwork for further statistical examination. The study applied descriptive statistics, specifically measures of central tendency and variability like mean and standard deviation, to each dataset. This allowed the researchers to grasp each dataset's central measure and diversity (Bhandari, 2023). The study also examined the minimum and maximum response values for each question, establishing their relationship to the variables presented in the study.

Additionally, this study incorporated correlational analysis further to explore the relationship between the variables under examination. Correlation analysis is a powerful tool for gauging the magnitude and direction of the linear association between two variables (Bhandari, 2023). Specifically, Spearman's Rank Correlation method was employed due to its effectiveness in measuring the strength and direction of association between two ranked variables (Gupta, 2023).

RESULTS

1. Independent Variables and Purchasing Intentions

Independent Variables	Mean	SD	r value	Description	R squared	p-value	Alpha	Decision	Remarks
Opinions on Products	3.07	0.51	0.772	Direct High Relationship	.586 or 58.6%	.000	.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Number of Followers	3.01	0.54							
Physical Attractiveness	3.08	0.52							

Table 1. Independent Variables and Purchasing Intentions

The table above examined whether physical attractiveness, opinions on a product, and the number of followers of Instagram influencers influence the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. According to the results, physical attractiveness emerged as the most influential variable in purchasing decisions, with the highest mean rating of 3.08 ($s=.52$), while the number of followers had the lowest rating at a mean of 3.01 ($s=.54$). Furthermore, the results indicated a strong positive correlation ($r=.772$) between the independent variables: opinions on products, number of followers, physical attractiveness, and purchasing intentions. Additionally, the study found statistically significant evidence ($p<.05$) to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting a meaningful relationship between the physical attractiveness, opinions on a product, number of followers of Instagram influencers, and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. These findings directly aligned with the study's second SOP, which investigated how physical attractiveness, opinions on a product, and the number of followers of Instagram influencers influence the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila.

2. Purchasing Intention and Gender

Variables	p-value	Alpha	Decision	Remarks
Purchasing Intention	.035	.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 2. Purchasing Intentions and Gender

The table presented an analysis of respondents' perceptions regarding the influence of Instagram influencers on the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private

university in Manila, categorized by gender. The results revealed statistically significant evidence ($p < .05$), indicating a difference in how male and female respondents perceive the impact of Instagram influencers on purchasing intentions. These findings directly supported the study's third statement of the problem, which investigated potential differences in the effect of Instagram influencers on the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila based on gender. The statistical analysis results revealed significant variations in perception between men and women regarding this influence.

3. Physical Attractiveness and Purchasing Intentions

Variables	r-value	Description	p-value	Alpha	Decision	Remarks
Physical Attractiveness and Purchasing Intentions	.475	Direct Moderate Relationship	.000	.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 3. Physical Attractiveness and Purchasing Intentions

The table above examined the correlation between the physical attractiveness of Instagram influencers and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. The results revealed a direct moderate correlation between these variables ($r = 0.475$). These results directly addressed the fourth statement of the problem, which explored the relationship between Instagram influencers' physical attractiveness and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. The statistical analysis provided compelling evidence to reject null hypothesis 4 ($p < 0.05$), highlighting a meaningful association between the physical attractiveness of Instagram influencers and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila.

4. Opinions on Products and Purchasing Intentions

Variables	r-value	Description	p-value	Alpha	Decision	Remarks
Opinions on products and Purchasing Intentions	.640	Direct Moderate Relationship	.000	.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 4. Opinions on Products and Purchasing Intentions

The table examined how the opinions of Instagram influencers about products relate to the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. The results indicated a moderate correlation between these variables ($r = 0.640$). This finding directly corresponded to the fifth statement of the problem, which investigated the relationship between Instagram influencers' product opinions and the purchasing

intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. The statistical analysis provided compelling evidence to reject the null hypothesis ($p < 0.05$), emphasizing a significant relationship between Instagram influencers' product opinions and the purchasing intentions of these students.

5. Number of Followers and Purchasing Intentions

Variables	r-value	Description	p-value	Alpha	Decision	Remarks
Number of Followers and Purchasing Intentions	0.591	Direct Moderate Relationship	.000	.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 5. Number of Followers and Purchasing Intentions

Table 5 examined the relationship between the number of followers of Instagram influencers and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. The results showed a direct moderate correlation between these variables ($r = 0.591$). This result directly aligned with the sixth statement of the problem, which investigated the relationship between Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila's purchasing intention and the number of followers of an Instagram influencer. The statistical analysis provided compelling evidence to reject the null hypothesis ($p < 0.05$), indicating a significant relationship between the number of followers of Instagram influencers and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila.

DISCUSSION

As evidenced by respondents in Table 1, Instagram influencers significantly influenced their purchasing decisions, highlighting the impact these influencers have on their buying intentions. Therefore, physical attractiveness, opinions on a product, and the number of followers of Instagram influencers significantly impact the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila, accounting for approximately 58.6% of the variance.

The data presented in Table 1 highlighted physical attractiveness as the most influential variable shaping the purchasing intention of Grade 12 ABM students. This finding was consistent with Rodrigues (2021), who noted a strong correlation between respondents' perceptions of social media influencers' attractiveness and purchasing intentions. Furthermore, Bakhtvar and Piri (2022) emphasized the positive impact of physical attractiveness, especially among young consumers, using celebrity influencers to drive purchasing intentions.

Moreover, the data from Table 1 emphasized the significant influence of Instagram influencers on the purchasing decisions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila, emphasizing their impact on buying intentions. This finding was backed up by the research of Patmawati and Sitompul (2022), who highlighted the effectiveness of influencer marketing on social media in capturing attention, raising awareness, and influencing followers. Husseino et al. (2022) also emphasized the profound influence of Instagram influencers on diverse online consumer purchasing intentions. Additionally, Toksari and Murutsoy (2019) demonstrated that influencer recommendations positively influence individual purchasing decisions, illustrating the impact of these influencers on consumer behavior and purchasing intentions.

The data in Table 2 highlighted variations in students' consumer behavior regarding purchasing products endorsed by social media influencers on Instagram, which differ based on gender. This finding aligned with the research conducted by Jeljeli et al. (2022), indicating that social influences positively impact both men and women, with a more pronounced effect observed among women. Similarly, Budacia et al. (2015) highlighted significant gender differences in how men and women interpret and respond to promotional messages and social influences in online marketing, emphasizing distinct patterns of engagement and perception between the two genders.

Additionally, Dalangin et al. (2021) suggested that female respondents tend to have a higher perception of social media influencers than male respondents, attributed partly to women's more frequent internet usage. This greater exposure to online content may lead women to develop stronger relationships with influencers and view their recommendations more favorably. Additionally, Nunes (2021) found that females exhibit greater trust perceptions (47.5%) compared to males (43.8%), indicating that women were more inclined to trust social media influencers when making purchasing decisions. Therefore, these findings highlighted the influence of gender on consumer perceptions and behaviors in the context of social media influencer marketing.

The result of Table 3 sheds light on how Instagram users were drawn to influencers they perceived as attractive, a factor that significantly influenced their popularity and fostered dedicated followers. This finding aligned with research conducted by (Kim & Park, 2023), which emphasized that influencers' attractiveness can stimulate followers' mimetic behavior and enhance their popularity and lifestyle. Similarly, studies by Ahmed & Mort (2016) and Branchik & Chowdhury (2017) suggested that consumers' positive attitudes toward desirable celebrities, influenced by their attractiveness, can impact purchase intentions.

Furthermore, Wiedmann and Mettenheim (2020) highlighted the importance of influencer trustworthiness and attractiveness as predictors of brand loyalty and purchasing intention. Additionally, Liu (2022) demonstrated that celebrity characteristics, particularly physical attractiveness, influence impulsive buying tendencies and purchase intentions, with purchase intention mediating in fostering consumers' impulsive purchases.

Table 4 on the other hand, highlighted the relationship between the product opinions of Instagram influencers and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila, addressing the fifth problem statement and challenging null hypothesis 5. This result was backed up by research from AlFarraj et al. (2021), which states that when influencers are viewed as experts, consumers are more likely to trust their recommendations and endorsements, influencing their purchase intentions.

Moreover, Casais and Conde (2023) noted that peers often seek out influencers for opinions and advice, establishing them as credible and influential figures in consumer decision-making. Moreover, Abdinagoro et al. (2020) found that consumers prioritize influencer endorsements over customer reviews, influenced by the perceived opinion leadership of influencers in shaping their purchasing decisions. Additionally, Alkan and Ulas (2022) discovered that influencers' positive or negative opinions about a product or brand can significantly impact the trust consumers place in them.

Lastly, Table 5 highlighted a substantial relationship between the number of followers of Instagram influencers and the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila, effectively addressing the sixth problem statement and rejecting null hypothesis six. This finding aligned with research by Chen et al. (2023), indicating that despite users' awareness of fake followers, follower count significantly influences consumer perceptions of an influencer's influencing power. Similarly, Casais and Conde (2023) concluded in their research that the higher an influencer's follower count, the more likely consumers were to adopt their recommendations, demonstrating their influence and persuasive impact.

Pittman and Abell (2021) proposed that purchase intentions and positive sentiments toward a product are positively influenced when endorsed by influencers with a large follower base. Additionally, Tamara et al. (2021) emphasized that the number of followers is critical for influencers to influence purchasing intentions on social media platforms significantly. Therefore, the follower counts of Instagram influencers played a pivotal role in shaping the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila, underscoring the importance of influencer reach and popularity in consumer decision-making processes.

Conclusions

To conclude, multiple tables revealed a strong influence of Instagram influencer marketing on the purchasing intentions of Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. Across various tables, key findings included the significant impact of influencer attractiveness on consumer behavior, with physical attractiveness being a critical factor shaping purchasing decisions. Additionally, there were notable gender-based variations in how students respond to influencer marketing, highlighting distinct patterns of engagement between male and female respondents. The data also emphasized the importance of influencer opinions, physical attractiveness, and follower counts in driving consumer purchasing intentions, underscoring influencers' significant role in shaping

consumer behavior and decision-making processes within this demographic. Together, these results highlighted the substantial influence of Instagram influencer marketing on consumer purchasing behaviors among Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila.

The researcher's investigation yielded crucial findings, leading to the following conclusions:

1. The study revealed that physical attractiveness was the most influential variable shaping consumers' perceptions and decisions about the products Instagram influencers endorse. This finding underscored how consumers associate attractive influencers with positive qualities such as desirability, success, and credibility, significantly impacting their purchasing decisions.

2. The study emphasized the effect of Instagram influencers on purchase intentions among Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. Survey results demonstrated a strong positive influence of influencer marketing, significantly increasing the likelihood of product purchases guided by these influencers.

3. The study revealed the importance of understanding gender differences in response to Instagram influencer marketing among Grade 12 ABM students in a private university in Manila. The study revealed distinct effects of gender on purchasing intentions, highlighting the need for tailored influencer strategies based on gender-specific preferences and perceptions.

4. The study confirmed the ELM's peripheral route theory, showing how follower count enhanced an influencer's credibility and trustworthiness. This information aligned with consumers relying on surface-level cues, like follower count, to make decisions.

5. The findings supported the ELM's peripheral cues, indicating that visual appeal and glamorous lifestyles portrayed by influencers influence students' purchasing decisions through the peripheral route of persuasion.

6. The study aligned with the ELM's central route, emphasizing consumers' trust in influencer opinions. This information reflected the thoughtful consideration of influencer content significantly shaping attitudes and behaviors toward products.

Recommendations

The study revealed the effectiveness of Instagram influencer marketing on the purchasing intention of Grade 12 ABM students. As a result, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Future researchers could recreate the study using a qualitative research design. This method would better understand other factors that affect Grade 12 students'

purchasing intentions. Researchers could gain deeper insights into how Instagram marketing shapes these students' decision-making processes when making purchases.

2. Future studies could broaden their scope beyond Manila to encompass students across various cities and regions in Luzon. Expanding the study's reach to a more diverse demographic might yield a broader consensus and more detailed results.

3. Future studies should compare influencer marketing effects across social media platforms beyond Instagram. Explore how influencer strategies differ on platforms like TikTok, YouTube, or Twitter, providing a comprehensive understanding of each platform's impact on Grade 12 ABM students' purchasing intentions.

4. Future researchers could investigate the longevity of Instagram influencers' impact on Grade 12 ABM students' purchasing decisions over time. Explore how this influence evolves and whether it maintains significance over extended periods.

5. Future Researchers should explore potential cultural or regional differences in how Grade 12 ABM students respond to influencer marketing. Investigate how cultural factors shape the influence of Instagram influencers among different demographics or regions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Protecting respondents and maintaining confidentiality were given particular attention, along with addressing their concerns about the survey. Here are the ethical considerations that were followed in the conduct of this study.

Voluntary Participation: Participation in this research was voluntary and optional, and no penalties or punishments were imposed upon respondents who opted not to participate. Respondents retained the right to withdraw from the study or discontinue participation at any point, even after it had begun, ensuring their informed consent throughout the research process.

Risks and Inconveniences: Personal information, such as name and gender identification, was requested from research respondents with guaranteed compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Participation in this research posed no significant risks physically, socially, or psychologically, and the questionnaire was impartial, ensuring the welfare of all respondents.

Provision for Injury or Related Illness: The participation of the respondents in the study was solely through an online survey. Hence, there was no provision for the risk of injury

or any illnesses, as the study was conducted through the use of Google Forms in the comfort of their own homes.

Conflict of Interest: To prevent bias in the study results, the researchers confirmed that they had no close personal relationships with any respondents, eliminating any sources of conflict of interest.

Data Management and Security Measures: The data gathered was stored in two different locations to have a backup plan for possible accidents like the disappearance of data. The primary storage for the data was on Google Drive.

Confidentiality: Respondents had the option to include or omit their names on the questionnaires and/or interview notes, as these materials were rendered anonymous through the assignment of code numbers. The respondent's complete name was not included in any questionnaires, and no details that could identify them were made public.

Disclosure of Publication Rights: The study's results may be presented at a conference or published in an academic journal. However, the respondents' identities are guaranteed to remain private and confidential.

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